

mixture was then poured on crushed ice, filtered and crystallised from ethanol to yield the products, melting points of compounds, R=phenyl, 280°; *o*-tolyl, 199; *m*-tolyl, 189°; *p*-tolyl, 210°; *o*-nitrophenyl, 176°; *m*-nitrophenyl, 205°; *p*-nitrophenyl, 217°; *o*-chlorophenyl, 220°; *m*-chlorophenyl, 190°; *p*-chlorophenyl, 200°; ν_{\max} 1 660 (CO), 1 620–1 530 (quinazoline nucleus) and 3 230–3 240 cm^{-1} (NH).

The purified product was screened for antibacterial activity by cup-plate method using a species of gram-positive (*S. aureus*) and gram-negative bacteria (*E. coli*). Testing was carried out in ethanol solution at the concentration of 10 mg ml^{-1} . The same method was adopted for determining *Klebeilla*. The zone of inhibition of both the activities of the test solution was recorded. The maximum zone of inhibition was obtained for *S. aureus*, in case of 2-(2'-styryl-4'-oxoquinazolino-6-ylamino)-4-(2'-methylphenylureido)-6-chloro-*s*-triazine. In case of *E. coli*, maximum zone of inhibition was recorded for 2-(2'-styryl-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino)-4-(3'-nitrophenylureido)-6-chloro-*s*-triazine, and against *Klebeilla*, maximum zone of inhibition was for 2-(2'-styryl-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino)-4-(4'-methylphenylureido)-6-chloro-*s*-triazine.

For *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *Klebeilla*, 2-[2'-mercapto-3'-(4"-methylphenyl)-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino]-4,6-bis(4'-nitrophenylureido)-*s*-triazine, 2-[2'-mercapto-3'-(4"-methylphenyl)-4'-oxoquinazolino-6-ylamino]-4,6-bis(2'-methylphenylureido)-*s*-triazine, and 2-[2'-mercapto-3'-(4"-methylphenyl)-4'-oxoquinazolino-6-ylamino]-4,6-bis(3'-chlorophenylureido)-*s*-triazine were recorded for the maximum zone of inhibition, respectively.

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Synthesis of 2-(6'-Methoxy-2'-methyl-4'-quinolinoxy)-4-(phenylureido)-6-(arylamino)-*s*-triazine and Study of their Antitubercular and Antibacterial Activity

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MANY alkaloids with a quinoline nucleus, the best known being quinine, are antimalarials. Various amino, halogeno, urea and thiourea derivatives of hydroxyquinolines possess biological activities¹.

With a view to get more active compounds we have synthesised 2-(6'-methoxy-2'-methyl-4'-quinolinoxy)-4-(phenylureido)-6-(arylamino)-*s*-triazine derivatives (1) and their biological activities were evaluated (Table 1). Antitubercular activity was carried out against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₈₇RV, and antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *S. aureus* and *Klebsiella*.

Experimental

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

2-(6'-Methoxy-2'-methyl-4'-quinolinoxy)-4,6-dichloro-*s*-triazine: 6-Methoxy-2-methyl-4-hydroxyquinoline (0.01 mol) dissolved in acetone was added in a well-stirred solution of cyanuric chloride (0.01 mol) dissolved in acetone. The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h at 0–5° at neutral pH. It was then poured on crushed ice, filtered and crystallised from alcohol, (74%), m.p. 160°.

2-(6'-Methoxy-2'-methyl-4'-quinolinoxy)-4-(phenylureido)-6-chloro-*s*-triazine: Phenylurea (0.01 mol) dissolved in acetone was added slowly to a solution of 2-(6'-methoxy-2'-methyl-4'-quinolinoxy)-4,6-dichloro-*s*-triazine (0.01 mol) in acetone at 30–40° and the mixture was stirred for 3 h at neutral pH. The reaction mixture was then poured on crushed ice, filtered and crystallised from alcohol, (69%), m.p. 212°.

General method for preparation of 2-(6'-methoxy-2'-methyl-4'-quinolinoxy)-4-(phenylureido)-6-(arylamino)-*s*-triazine: A mixture of 2-(4'-methoxy-2'-methyl-4'-quinolinoxy)-4-(phenylureido)-6-chloro-*s*-triazine (0.01 mol) and various amines (0.01 mol) in dioxane was refluxed at 80–90° for 3 h maintaining neutral pH. The reaction mixture was then poured on crushed ice, filtered and crystallised from ethanol. The physical and antibacterial activity

data are presented in Table 1. All the compounds, in general, exhibited the following ir bands : 820–830 (C₂N₃), 1 280–1 275 (C–O–C), 1 670–1 690 (NH–C), 1 150–1 175 (C–O) and 1 310–1 350 (C–N).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Zone of inhibition (mm) ^a			M. t ^{**}
				<i>E. c.</i>	<i>S. a.</i>	<i>K.</i>	
1.	Aniline	240	71	1.5	0.5	1.0	+
2.	<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline	252	72	0.5	0.0	0.0	+
3.	<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	240	69	2.5	0.5	2.0	+
4.	<i>o</i> -Toluidine	245	76	2.0	2.5	1.0	+
5.	<i>p</i> -Toluidine	232	68	1.5	2.0	1.0	0
6.	<i>o</i> -Anisidine	220	72	0.5	0.0	0.5	+
7.	<i>p</i> -Anisidine	168	78	1.0	0.5	0.5	+
8.	<i>o</i> -Nitroaniline	226	67	3.0	2.0	0.5	0
9.	<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline	200	69	1.5	2.0	2.5	+
10.	<i>p</i> -Bromoaniline	273	78	1.5	2.5	1.0	+

^a *E. c.* = *E. coli*, *S. a.* = *S. aureus*, *K.* = *Klebsiella*,

^{**} *M. t.* = *M. tuberculosis* H₃₇RV; (+) = positive.

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Synthesis and Biological Activity of 2-(4'-Methoxyanilino)-4-[N⁴-(N¹-(6'-methoxy-3'-pyridazinyl)sulphanilamido)]-6-(arylthioureido)-5-triazines

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s-Triazine¹ nucleus has been the subject of several investigations in order to study its potential as antibacterial agent. Sulphonamides form a separate group among the antibacterials. Furthermore, since a number of thiourea derivatives are reported to possess biological activities², it was anticipated that the combined presence of N–C=S and sulphanilamido groupings in a *s*-triazine ring may enhance

antibacterial activity³. Hence the title *s*-triazine derivatives (1a–j) were synthesised to study their potentiality as antibacterial agents.

Cyanuric chloride and *p*-anisidine were condensed in equimolar proportions. The resultant product was reacted with sulphamethoxypyridazine followed by reaction with arylthiourea to yield the corresponding 2-(4'-methoxyanilino)-4-[N⁴-(N¹-(6'-methoxy-3'-pyridazinyl)sulphanilamido)]-6-(arylthioureido)-*s*-triazines. Structures of the compounds were established by elemental and spectral data (Table 1).

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin–Elmer 157 spectrophotometer. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc.

2-(4'-Methoxyanilino)-4,6-dichloro-*s*-triazine: To a stirred solution of cyanuric chloride (1.84 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone at 0–5°, a solution of *p*-anisidine (1.23 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone was added and neutral pH was maintained. The stirring was continued at the same temperature (0–5°) for 2 h. The solution was then treated with crushed ice and the resulting solid was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol, (85%), m.p. 150°.

2-(4'-Methoxyanilino)-4-[N⁴-(N¹-(6'-methoxy-3'-pyridazinyl)sulphanilamido)]-6-chloro-*s*-triazine: To a stirred solution of 2-(4'-methoxyanilino)-4,6-dichloro-*s*-triazine (2.71 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone at 35°, a solution of sulphamethoxypyridazine (2.80 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone was added dropwise for 0.5 h and neutral pH was maintained. The temperature was then gradually raised to 45° during 2 h. The solution was then poured in ice-cold water and the resulting solid was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol, (78%), m.p. > 300°.

General procedure for preparation of 2-(4'-methoxyanilino)-4-[N⁴-(N¹-(6'-methoxy-3'-pyridazinyl)sulphanilamido)]-6-(arylthioureido)-*s*-triazine: A mixture of 2-(4'-methoxyanilino)-4-[N⁴-(N¹-(6'-methoxy-3'-pyridazinyl)sulphanilamido)]-6-chloro-*s*-triazine (5.15 g, 0.01 mol) and arylthiourea (0.01 mol) in acetone was refluxed at 80–90° for 3 h. The solution was then treated with crushed ice and the resulting solid was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol; ν_{\max} 820, 1 410 (C₂N₃), 1 500 (thiourea C–N), 1 240 (C–O–C), 1 135 (S–O) and 1 550–1 560 cm⁻¹ (sec. amine NH).